

STRENGTHENING CLINICAL TRIAL REGULATORY AND ETHICAL REVIEW OVERSIGHT IN EAST AFRICA.

D2.3 Joint Inspections Conduct

Project acronym: ACCESSAFRICA 2

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Consortium Partners:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	Uganda National Health Research Organisation	UNHRO	Uganda
3.	Partner	Jimma University	JU	Ethiopia
4.	Partner	Uganda National Council for Science and Technology	UNCST	Uganda
5.	Partner	National Drug Authority	NDA	Uganda

Introduction

One of the objectives of Work Package 2, is to improve the coordination of NDA, UNCST, and Research Ethics Committees through the conduct of joint inspections for studies that undergo joint reviews.

Joint GCP (Good Clinical Practice) inspections are conducted to ensure consistency in the application of GCP standards. In addition, Joint inspections allow clinical trial regulators to pool resources and expertise thus making inspections more efficient. This is especially important when considering complex multisite clinical trials. Joint inspections often generate more knowledge about the conduct of clinical trials which fosters collaboration and mutual understanding among clinical trials regulators. This collaboration is key when addressing challenges such as data integrity, participant safety, and compliance with GCP guidelines.

Accordingly, the National Drug Authority with support from the Access Africa 2 project coordinated the conduct of Joint GCP inspection for the OTAC clinical trial (CTA 0189) in collaboration with other regulators i.e., Uganda National Council of Science and Technology (UNCST) and the Research and Ethics Committee of Uganda Virus Research Institute (UVRI).

The OTAC trial is a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial to evaluate the safety and efficacy of HIVIG given in addition to Standard of Care (SOC) among adults ≥ 55 years of age or adults ≥ 18 years of age who have an underlying immunosuppressive condition diagnosed early in the course of their COVID-19 disease (≤ 5 days since symptom onset and ≤ 5 days from microbiological diagnosis), who are not hospitalized or in the process of being hospitalized at baseline.

Although there are multiple clinical trials currently ongoing in Uganda, this particular clinical trial was selected to undergo joint inspection following a risk-based approach. The OTAC study is a multisite clinical trial involving a vulnerable population of elderly participants (≥ 55 years of age) and immunocompromised adults ≥ 18 years of age diagnosed early in the course of their COVID-19 disease. In addition, the investigational product is a novel biological product which necessitates more stringent regulation compared to registered products.

Inspection team

Name	Designation
Dr Helen Byomire Ndagije	Co-PI – AccessAfrica2, Director Product Safety – National Drug Authority
Diana Kesi Nakitto	Manager Clinical Trials, National Drug Authority
David Walusimbi	Coordinator/ Inspector of Drugs – National Drug Authority
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Dr Robert Ssekubugu	Member, Uganda Virus Research Institute – Research Ethics Committee

1. Administrative Information

Type of Inspection	Joint GCP inspection
Purpose	To verify compliance with the clinical trial protocol, conditions of the Clinical Trial Certificate, and the principles of Good Clinical Practice
Investigational Product(s) Medicinal	Anti-Coronavirus Hyperimmune Intravenous Immunoglobulin
Name and full address of the Principal Investigator	Dr. Joseph Lutaakome MRC/UVRI and LSHTM Uganda Research Unit Plot 51-59 Nakiwogo Road, Entebbe P.O Box 49, Entebbe Tel; +256 772 820463
Clinical Trial Identification	
Sponsor	University of Minnesota
Trial protocol number/ Version number and date	Version 3.0 dated March 08, 2023
NDA Identifier	CTA 0189 (OTAC Trial)
Trial protocol title	An International Multicenter, Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled Trial of the Safety and Efficacy of Anti-Coronavirus Hyperimmune

	Intravenous Immunoglobulin for the Treatment of Adult Outpatients in Early Stages of COVID-19, Version 3.0 dated March 08, 2023
Site details	MRC/UVRI and LSHTM Uganda Research Unit – Entebbe Regional Referral Hospital Grade A
Number of Investigator Sites	6 Sites in Uganda <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MRC/UVRI and LSHTM Uganda Research Unit-Entebbe 2. MRC/UVRI and LSHTM Uganda Research Unit-Masaka 3. Joint Clinical Research Centre (JCRC) - Lubowa 4. St. Francis Hospital, Nsambya 5. SICRA based at Lira Regional Referral Hospital 6. Makerere Lung Institute based at Mulago National Referral Hospital
Number of Participants	17 Participants at the time of inspection
Date(s) of Inspection	19 th to 20 th February 2024
Other partners	

2. Background

The OTAC trial is a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial to evaluate the safety and efficacy of hIVIG given in addition to Standard of Care (SOC) among adults ≥ 55 years of age or adults ≥ 18 years of age who have an underlying immunosuppressive condition diagnosed early in the course of their COVID-19 disease (≤ 5 days since symptom onset and ≤ 5 days from microbiological diagnosis), who are not hospitalized or in the process of being hospitalized at baseline. There are two study design strata, and enrolment into a given stratum is pre-specified before randomization. Stratum 1 is defined by the use of any prescribed SOC treatment or supportive care other than Direct-Acting Antiviral (DAA) or other anti-SARS-CoV-2 agents, which may include no treatments. Stratum 2 is defined by the use of prescribed SOC that includes DAA or other anti-SARS-CoV2 agents that are recommended for use by established national or international COVID-19 treatment guidelines (e.g., the US National Institutes of Health [NIH], Infectious Diseases Society of America [IDSA], or the World Health Organization [WHO]), with or without other forms of SOC.

2.1 Trial Objectives.

2.1.1 Primary Objective

The primary objective of the trial is to compare the safety and efficacy of a single infusion of hyperimmune immunoglobulin (hIVIG) versus placebo, each given with standard of care (SOC), on clinical status after seven days among outpatients with recently diagnosed SARS-CoV-2 infection. Two hypotheses will be tested to address this primary objective, which compares the primary endpoint among two study populations: 1) participants where a direct-acting antiviral (DAA) or other anti-SARS-CoV-2 agent was not prescribed as part of SOC treatment (stratum 1); and 2) all randomized participants (stratum 1 and stratum 2 combined).

Stratum 2 is defined by prescribed treatments in SOC that include: DAA or other anti-SARS-CoV2 agents that are recommended for use by established national or international COVID-19 treatment guidelines.

2.1.2 Study status at the time of inspection:

The target number of participants is 352 participants and 17 participants had been enrolled at the time of inspection.

3 The regulatory approvals for the study are summarized in the table below:

Regulatory Approvals	Document No	Approved on	Expiry
Initial Approvals			
National Drug Authority	CTC 0189/2021	17 November 2021	17 November 2022
Uganda Virus Research Institute-REC	GC/127/846	31 August 2021	31 August 2022
Uganda National Council of Science and Technology (UNCST)	HS1715ES	04 October 2021	04 October 2022
Current Approvals			
National Drug Authority	CTC 0189/2023	17 November 2023	17 November 2024
Uganda Virus Research Institute-REC	GC/127/846	21 August 2023	30 August 2024
Uganda National Council of Science and Technology (UNCST)	HS1715ES	29 November 2022	04 October 2024

4 Reason for the Inspection

This was a Joint Good Clinical Practice (GCP) routine Inspection that was carried out at the site conducting the clinical trial titled, “An International Multicenter, Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled Trial of the Safety and Efficacy of Anti-Coronavirus Hyperimmune Intravenous Immunoglobulin for the Treatment of Adult Outpatients in Early Stages of COVID-19” from 19th to 21st February 2024.

4.1 Scope of Inspection

The methods used during this inspection were:

- i) Site/premise inspection
- ii) Document review
- iii) Interviewing key personnel

The documentation and processes reviewed included:

- i) General trial documents: Protocol, sample Case Report Forms (CRFs), Standard Operating Procedures, Ethics Committee, and regulatory correspondence.
- ii) Documentation relating to the investigational medicinal product handling, storage, and accountability.
- iii) Laboratory records.

5 Observations

5.1 Personnel Management and Training

During the inspection, the inspection team interacted with the following people involved in the trial: The Principal Investigator, Study Investigator, Study Coordinator, Pharmacists, Field worker Team lead, Field Technician Assistant, Study Administrator, and the Pharmacy Technician.

All Study personnel were duly delegated by the Principal Investigator and a Delegation of Duties log for the study version 1.0 dated 10th June 2021 was available at the site

Study Personnel had been trained in good clinical practice and the study protocol training on the preparation of the Investigational Medicinal Product.

5.2 Facilities and Equipment

The study clinic was located at Entebbe Grade A Hospital. The Clinic had a reception and an aerated waiting area, a Principal Investigator's room, a Doctor's room, a Pharmacy office, a data room, a file room, a Pharmacy store, and a Phlebotomy room.

The Emergency room was well-equipped with emergency equipment, drugs, and two beds. The emergency facilities were easily accessible to all staff to allow for timely emergency care for the participants who would need it.

5.3 Laboratory

The clinical trial site had access to the MRC/UVRI and LSHTM Central Diagnostic Laboratory Services (CDLS) where all laboratory tests for the clinical trial were carried out. The entry to the lab had biometric access control restricting unauthorized access to the premises. The laboratory had a central specimen reception area that was spacious, tidy, and well-furnished where samples from the study were received, checked for suitability, and then transferred to the Biorepository for storage before shipping.

The different processing laboratory units were fully furnished with state-of-the-art equipment. The equipment used was well calibrated and within the service period as verified on the stickers. The laboratory had a freezer room that was equipped with -80°C freezers for the storage of samples after sample processing in line with the study protocol. In the event of a power outage, there was evidence of a backup power source for the laboratory.

5.4 Documentation and Systems for Quality Control and Quality Assurance (QC/QA)

At the research site, the Investigator Site File (ISF) binder was well organized each with a table of contents to allow for retrieval and traceability. Documents such as delegation log, updated protocol, pharmacy manual, templates of consent forms, regulatory approvals, and standard operating procedures among others were available to demonstrate Quality Control and Quality Assurance processes. The screening and enrolment logs were on file and it was verified that all the Informed Consent Forms for the study participants have been appropriately signed and dated. All the participant files for this site were reviewed by the inspection team.

There was compliance with regulatory administrative aspects, up-to-date Good Clinical Practice training, Annual Practising Licenses, NDA, UNCST and Research Ethics approvals, importation permits, and Verification Certificates which were all verified at the time of the inspection.

5.5 Investigational Medicinal Products (IMP) storage, handling and disposal

The Investigational Medicinal Product (IMP) was imported by MRC/UVRI and LSHTM Uganda Research Unit and the shipping records were available and up-to-date. It was stored in the IMP Pharmacy at Entebbe Grade A hospital. Access to the pharmacy premises and IMP storage area was controlled by a double lock and key and a biometric system and was restricted to authorized personnel. The trial pharmacists and pharmacy technicians were responsible for handling the study drug inventory. Accountability records were version-controlled and up-to-date.

The study had received the investigational product in compliance with the National Drug Authority importation guidelines and a verification certificate and an imported goods authorization report were available on file.

The Investigational Medicinal Product (IMP) was stored in a 2-8°C refrigerator and was prepared in the Class 2 Biosafety Cabinet in the Pharmacy and then transported to the emergency room for infusion. To ensure temperature control in the pharmacy, there were Air conditioners in the pharmacy. Temperature monitoring in the room and fridges was done using digital min and max thermometers.

5.6 Safety Monitoring and Reporting Mechanisms

The system for detecting, reporting, and managing Adverse Events was well-detailed in the protocol and standard operating procedure for managing Adverse Events. The grading table in use was the DAIDS AE Grading Table. There were no recorded Serious Adverse Events (SAE) at the time of inspection

5.7 Clinical Trials Insurance

There was a clinical trial insurance policy from a local insurance company that was adequate and still valid at the time of inspection.

5.8 Monitoring and Auditing

A study Monitoring Plan was available at the site. The UVRI-REC had conducted one (1) monitoring visit on 16 December 2023 as per the schedule and the report was available at the time of inspection.

5.9 Data Management

REDCap Version 12.4.12 was being used as the database for data management of the OTAC study. The electronic system had the properties of controlling access through the use of a unique password, enabling real-time data entry and case reporting.

6 Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the areas inspected, the people met and the documents reviewed, and the findings of the inspection, including the observations listed in the Inspection Report, a decision on the compliance of the study with ICH E6(R2) GCP guidelines will be made after the facility's response to the observations communicated. The facility was advised to respond to the observations and submit a corrective action and preventive action (CAPA) report for consideration by the inspection team.

Following the inspection, the team came up with a number of recommendations for continuous improvement of the joint inspection mechanism:

1. To establish regular monitoring procedures to ensure ongoing compliance with GCP and other regulatory requirements.
2. To foster open communication and collaboration among all stakeholders involved in clinical trials, including, investigators, institutional review boards (IRBs), and regulatory authorities to enable the identification and resolution of clinical trial challenges more effectively.
3. To increase the number of clinical trials that are monitored under the joint inspection platform as a means of continuous improvement for regulators which enhances clinical trial quality and compliance.
4. Strengthen regulatory liaison by conducting joint GCP Inspections as a means of proactively maintaining collaborations with other regulatory authorities.
5. To establish a follow up and monitoring mechanism for corrective and preventive action following joint inspections.

7 Reference texts

1. An International Multicentre, Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled Trial of the Safety and Efficacy of Anti-Coronavirus Hyperimmune Intravenous Immunoglobulin for the Treatment of Adult Outpatients in Early Stages of COVID-19. Version 3.0 dated March 08, 2023.
2. The National Drug Policy and Authority Act. CAP 206
3. The National Drug Policy and Authority (Conduct of Clinical Trials) Regulations, 2014.
4. National Guidelines for Research Involving Humans as Research Participants- July 2014.
5. World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki, in the version, October 2013 WMA: Declaration of Helsinki - Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects.
6. ICH-GCP E6 (R2). International Conference on Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline for Good Clinical Practice E6 (R2).

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